

doi 10.5281/zenodo.10432522

Vol. 06 Issue 11 Nov - 2023

Manuscript ID: #01173

Impact of school inspection and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of school inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. Two research questions and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The research design that guided the study was the cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 2474 staff drawn from 81 public secondary schools in Abuja. The sample size of the study consisted of 693 respondents. The researcher developed an instrument for data collection from the respondents. The instrument was tagged 'Questionnaire on School Inspection and Teacher Job Performance' (QSITJP). Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Pearson's product moment correlation was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja and there was a significant impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja. The study recommended that the Federal Capital Territory Secondary Education Board should mandate all quality assurance officers in Abuja to submit the reports of their full-general inspection activities monthly to help the board develop strategies on how to strengthen the identified teachers' weak areas to enable them to perform their teaching job effectively.

KEYWORDS:

School Inspection, Teachers' Job Performance, Full-general Inspection and Subject-based Inspection.

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Introduction

School inspection is an inevitable activity in every educational institution. It is the assessment of the general education programme to provide a way forward for certain school problems by assisting teachers to improve their instructional delivery. School inspection involves a collaborative arrangement in which a team of quality assurance officers visit schools periodically to monitor and ensure that the set standards of secondary education are well implemented through effective teaching and coordination of school activities (Usman & Mainoma, 2016). The essence of school inspection is to facilitate complete compliance with the laid down rules and regulations as stated in the National Policy on Education. During school inspection, the quality assurance officers compile reports and suggest the way forward on the areas of weaknesses observed in a particular school. School inspection is an official visit of the personnel from the inspectorate department of the Ministry of Education to identify the problems experienced by teachers, principals and students to enable them to provide solutions to such problems so that the standard of education can be sustained and maintained continuously (Iyala & Sani, 2022).

School inspection involves the measurement, testing and assessment of educational activities in the school system to improve the standards and quality of educational services received by students. Inspection of the school consists of a series of activities like monitoring and assessing the quality of instructional delivery, school management and the physical learning environment. Adetula (2015) asserted that school inspection is the assessment of the state of teaching and learning-related issues in an educational institution to sustain the laid down standards that are needed for achieving the school objectives. Inspection is a process of overseeing a school's activities by ensuring that they are performed based on the stipulated guidelines to enable schools to contribute positively towards the attainment of the overall educational goals through effective teaching and learning. In Nigeria, quality assurance officers are education officers who have been trained in the field of education. They are responsible for enforcing the effective implementation of curriculum goals, proper use of school resources, guidance and monitoring of teachers' activities to ensure that schools adhere strictly to the objectives, guidelines, standards and government policies on secondary education (Badare, 2017).

School inspection consists of the activities of personnel from the inspectorate department in the Ministry of Education that is characterized by checkmating the teaching and learning process of teachers in the areas of planning of lessons, instructional delivery, classroom management and use of instructional materials. It guides and directs teachers to choose the appropriate teaching methods and develop strategies that will help to improve teaching and learning activities. Inspection is characterized by overseeing, directing, controlling, reporting and assessing the activities of the school system to achieve the goals of secondary education. Inspection is an activity that enhances effective teaching because it facilitates the improvement of teachers' professional behaviour, attitudes, mode of teaching and relationship with students (Eya & Chukwu, 2019).

Teachers in secondary schools in Abuja like their counterparts in other states in Nigeria are inspected through different approaches. Among the approaches are classroom visitation, assessment of lesson plans, checking and interacting with students, school records, checking of class attendance registers, assessment of physical facilities, ascertaining the state of library facilities, interactions with teachers and principals to identify the challenges facing them and so on. Post-inspection meetings are normally held between the quality assurance officers and teachers to enable the quality assurance officers to point out different weak areas they must have observed during the inspection exercise to teachers (Enaigbe, 2019).

The handbook for inspection of schools in Nigeria that was drafted in 2007 identified different types of inspection which include full-general inspection, subject-based inspection, registration or recognition inspection, advisory inspection, evaluation inspection, block inspection, mass inspection and follow-up inspection. This study focused on full-general inspection and subject-based inspection because they are more relevant in enhancing the job performance of teachers than the other types of school inspection.

The full-general inspection involves a complete diagnostic and situational analysis of schools. During the full-general inspection, the entire activities of a school are completely reviewed to identify the weak areas that need to be strengthened or given adequate attention. Full-general inspection is conducted to suggest the way forward for any identifiable problem by the quality assurance officers. Full-general inspections could be carried out at the pre-primary, primary and secondary levels of education. Olowale (2016) conducted a study and found that interaction between teachers and quality assurance officers during full-general inspection influences teachers' classroom performance. It consists of a team of specialists in different fields of study such as guidance and counselling, management, auditors, subject experts and curriculum designers. Before the arrival of the quality assurance officers, the date and time will be communicated to the affected schools in advance. For a thorough school inspection, full-general inspection exercises need to be carried out for two or more days. Every educational institution is expected to undergo full-general inspection every two years. Oshoke (2017) found out that all forms of inspection influence the high performance of teachers and students in secondary schools in Edo State.

Subject-based inspection is a specialized inspection conducted by quality assurance officers in subject areas in which they are specialists. It requires the quality assurance officers to visit and obtain information about teaching and learning situations from teachers in their subject areas and other aspects of school endeavour to enable them to make provision for improving the weak areas through planning and formulation of policies that would maintain the standard of teaching in various subjects that are contained in the curriculum. Oshoke (2017) maintained that all forms of inspection influence the high performance of teachers and students in secondary schools in Edo State. Textbooks, instructional materials, qualifications of teachers and teaching methods are the major focus of subject-based inspection. This type of inspection is normally planned and carried out using the following factors according to Akinde (2016:45):

1. The trends of students performance in a specific subject in the national examinations by schools;
2. The inspector's work programme;
3. Enquiring about the needs of teachers in their subjects to enable them to carry out effective teaching; and
4. The assessment of how the curriculum in each subject is interpreted and implemented by teachers.

The central idea of school inspection whether full-general, recognition, followed-up, subject-based and so on is to facilitate effective teaching and learning in the secondary school system. Job performance is the manner through which staff in an organization discharges the responsibilities assigned to them to achieve the organizational objectives. In the school system, a teacher's job performance refers to the tasks undertaken by a teacher at any given time in the school to achieve both the classroom objectives and the entire objectives of the educational system. Job performance by teachers could be classified as poor, low, moderate and high based on the level of their enthusiasm, commitment and dedication to work (Adeyemi, 2015). Adeyemi (2017) outlined the indices of teacher job performance to include effective teaching, lesson note preparation, effective use of the scheme of

work, effective supervision, classroom management skills, regular giving of assignments to students, monitoring of students' work as well as control and discipline of students. As a result, teacher job performance could be measured through the annual reports of their activities in the areas of undertaking their classroom teaching responsibilities, lesson preparation, lesson presentation, mastery of subject matter, competence, teachers' commitment to the job and active participation in school extra-curricular activities. Teachers are bestowed with the role of imparting knowledge, skills, attitudes and techniques to students. It is the prime responsibility of teachers to help students acquire the basic knowledge, skills, attitudes, ideas and values that will help them to be useful to themselves and the society at large. It is the responsibility of teachers to create the desired changes in students' behaviour. Students are guided by teachers through various planned activities to enable the students to acquire the highest learning experiences and discipline needed to be successful in the world of work (Ezenwaji, 2019). As observed by the researcher, teachers in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria are under-performing the above responsibilities. Hence, this study investigated the impact of school inspection on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Education in the modern world has become more complex. The complexities of educational systems and their institutions in Nigeria including Abuja have witnessed series of changes in the areas of high students' enrolment, examination malpractices, indiscipline among staff and students, inadequate provision of educational resources and poor students' academic performance. The prevalence of the above problems in public secondary schools in Abuja necessitates viable programmes and strategies of quality assurance and control in the form of regular school inspections. Despite the effort of the creation of an inspectorate office in each of the Area Councils in Abuja, stakeholders in educational sectors such as the principals, teachers, parents and traditional rulers have raised alarm over the poor performance of students in both the internal and external examinations. Such poor performance of students in different examinations may be traced to poor quality of instructional delivery by teachers. If teacher performance is poor, it, therefore, means that inspection activities especially subject-based inspection which is aimed at identifying the qualifications and assessing the performance of teachers with the aim of making suggestions for improvement are also very poor.

It is disheartening to note that most of the quality assurance officers in Nigeria are incompetent and lack the basic knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for effective school inspection as the majority of them are not professionally trained as educational quality assurance officers. Apart from not having qualified quality assurance officers, the few available ones are grossly inadequate to the growing number of schools being established in Abuja. The few available quality assurance officers are saddled with too many workloads which makes it difficult for them to carry out effective and successful inspection of the school system to improve the job performance of teachers. Worried by the above problems, the study investigated the impact of school inspection on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the impact of school inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were as follows:

1. To determine the impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.
2. To ascertain the impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

1. What is the impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja?
2. What is the impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

HO₂: There is no significant impact of subject-based inspection on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Methodology

The study was guided by the cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 2474 (81 principals and 2379 teachers) drawn from all the 81 public secondary schools of the six Area Councils in Abuja. The sample size of the study consisted of 693 respondents (45 principals and 648 teachers) drawn from 45 schools. The simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents for the study to avoid bias. The researchers developed an instrument for data collection from the respondents. The instrument was tagged 'Questionnaire on School Inspection and Teachers' Job Performance' (QSITJP). The questionnaire consisted of 14 items designed based on Likert's 5-point rating scale given as follows: SA=strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), D=Disagree (3), SD= Strongly Disagree (2) and U= Undecided (1). The questionnaire was validated and the logical validity index of 0.88 was obtained. The coefficient of internal consistency of 0.70 was obtained as the reliability index after pilot testing the instrument. The period of three days was given to the respondents to respond to the items after which the researcher retrieved the questionnaires from them. However, 23 respondents representing 3.31% rendered their questionnaires invalid but the number of invalid questionnaires was inadequate to affect the validity and reliability of the findings of this study. Descriptive statistics of means and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. The scale mean for accepting or rejecting any item was 3.00. Any item below 3.00 was classified as 'agreed' while the items above 3.00 were classified as 'disagreed'. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer each of the research questions as presented on Tables 1 and 2 below:

Research Question One: What is the impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the Responses on the Impact of Full-General Inspection on Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	Std.	Decision
1.	Teachers are properly guided on how to manage students' behaviour during lessons through full-general inspection to improve their job performance.	120	95	200	250	5	2.35	0.47	Disagreed

2.	Quality assurance officers guide teachers through full-general inspection to identify their weak areas that need to be strengthened to enhance effective teaching.	100	96	210	260	4	2.27	0.55	Disagreed
3.	School activities are reviewed through full-general inspection to provide teachers with the required resources needed to facilitate proper teaching and learning.	110	80	210	268	2	2.38	0.62	Disagreed
4.	Effective teaching could be enhanced when quality assurance officers carefully assess the notes given to students by teachers use them.	300	180	90	99	1	2.50	0.55	Accepted
5.	Wrong teaching methods observed by quality assurance officers during full-general inspection exercises are politely corrected to boost teachers' morale and enhance their job performance.	130	100	190	250	0	2.45	0.39	Disagreed
6.	Teachers are properly guided and directed to plan their lessons adequately by quality assurance officers.	121	99	192	248	10	2.42	0.74	Disagreed
7.	Quality assurance officers guide and coach teachers on the effective use of instructional materials during lesson delivery.	144	96	200	225	5	2.34	0.65	Disagreed
Aggregate Mean							2.38	0.56	Disagreed

Scale Mean 3.00

Table 1 showed that item 1 has a mean score of 2.35 and a standard deviation of 2.37, item 2 has a mean score of 2.27 and standard deviation of 0.55, item 3 has a mean score of 2.38 and a standard deviation of 0.12, item 4 has a mean score of 2.35 and standard deviation of 2.50, item 5 has the mean score of 2.45 and standard deviation of 0.39, item 6 has the mean score of 2.42 and standard deviation of 0.74, while item 7 has the mean score of 2.34 and standard deviation of 0.65. The aggregate mean of 2.38 is below the scale mean of 3.00, this means that there is a low impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

Research Question Two: What is the impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the Responses on the Impact of Subject-Based Inspection on Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	Std.	Decision
8	Teachers are inspected by specialists during the subject-based inspection which helps them to have in-depth knowledge of their various subjects.	70	50	196	350	4	2.28	0.44	Disagreed
9	Teachers learn new teaching skills that enhance the mastery of their subjects during the subject-based inspection.	190	290	90	80	20	2.52	0.58	Agreed
10	Subject-based inspection is properly used to guide teachers to improve their job performance.	130	60	210	270	0	2.23	0.39	Disagreed
11	Teachers acquire more knowledge on how to select and use teaching aids on specific topics through subject-based inspection.	90	80	230	268	2	2.28	0.59	Disagreed
12	Teachers are properly guided on how to select the appropriate textbooks required for preparing their lessons through subject-based inspection.	120	80	220	250	0	2.32	0.60	Disagreed
13	Lesson delivery is done in a half-hazard manner by teachers due to poor subject-based inspection.	260	150	114	138	8	2.50	0.35	Accepted

14	Visitation of teachers by quality assurance officers who are specialists in their subjects during lessons' delivery could help to improve the classroom management techniques.	110	100	160	290	10	2.34	0.24	Disagreed
Aggregate Mean							2.35	0.45	Disagreed
Scale Mean 3.00									

Table 2 revealed that item 8 has a mean score of 2.28 and a standard deviation of 0.44, item 9 has a mean score of 2.52 and a standard deviation of 0.58, item 10 has the mean score of 2.23 and standard deviation of 0.39, item 11 has a mean score of 2.28 and standard deviation of 0.59, item 12 has a mean score of 2.32 and standard deviation of 0.60 item 13 has a mean score of 2.42, and standard deviation of 2.50 while item 14 has the mean score of 2.34 and standard deviation of 0.24. It is observed from the above analysis that the aggregate mean of 2.35 is below the scale mean of 3.00, this, therefore, demonstrated that there is a poor impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

Testing of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested using ANOVA at a 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant influence impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

Table 3: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing the Impact of Full-General Inspection on teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Abuja, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-Value	Sig. Level	Decision
Between Groups	430.091	18	86.319	5.735	.039	0.05	Significant
Within Groups	1726.489	675	49.747				
Total	2156.580	693					

Dfs = 16,252; hence, $p < .05$ Significant

Table 3 above shows that the p-value of 0.039 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis one was not accepted which means that there is a significant impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja (dfs = 18,693; F-calculated = 5.735; $p = 0.39$; $p < 0.05$; Significant)

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant impact of subject-based inspection on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria

Table 4: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing the Impact of Subject-Based Inspection and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Abuja, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-Value	Sig. Level	Decision
Between Groups	430.091	18	86.319	5.521	.042	0.05	Significant
Within Groups	1726.489	675	49.747				
Total	2156.580	693					

Dfs = 18,675; $p < .05$ Significant

Table 4 above shows that the p-value of 0.042 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, null hypothesis two was the null hypothesis was rejected which means that there was a significant impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja (dfs = 16,252; F-calculated = 5.521; $p = 0.42$; hence, $p < 0.05$; Significant).

Summary of Major Findings

The following is the summary of the findings:

1. There is a significant impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.
2. There is a significant impact of subject-based inspection and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of hypothesis one showed that there is a significant impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The findings of this study agreed with Olowale (2016) who concluded that interaction between teachers and quality assurance officers during full-general inspection influences teachers' classroom performance. The findings of the study also agreed with Oshoke (2017) who found that all forms of inspection influence the high performance of teachers and students in secondary schools in Edo State. The full-general inspection involves a complete diagnostic and situational analysis of schools. During the full-general inspection, the entire activities of a school are completely reviewed to identify the weak areas that need to be strengthened or given adequate attention. The full-general inspection is conducted to suggest the way forward for any identifiable problem by the quality assurance officers. It consists of a team of specialists in different fields of study such as guidance and counselling, management, auditors, subjects experts and curriculum designers. Before the arrival of the quality assurance officers, the date and time will be communicated to the affected schools in advance. It is the type of inspection that is designed to evaluate the broad spectrum of school activities. Full-general inspection involves a full diagnostic and situational analysis of the institution and it is always conducted with a view of examining the strengths and weaknesses or limitations of an institution by suggesting interventions to be administered for the improvement of educational standards. This type of inspection entails the comprehensive assessment of all aspects of a school. Since the full-general inspection is comprehensive, it requires a large team of quality assurance officers so that every aspect of the school system can be thoroughly inspected. This type of inspection takes place within a school for about four to five days. The number of days to be used and the number of persons involved in the full-general inspection depends on the nature of a school to be inspected with specific considerations to the size of a school, its location, type of school (whether pure science, technical or conventional school). The full-general inspection is not conducted in a hurry as it is aimed at making suggestions that will sustain the growth of a school at the present and in the future.

Furthermore, the findings of hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant impact of subject-based inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings of the study confirmed the position of Oshoke (2017) who maintained that all forms of inspection influence the high performance of teachers and students in secondary schools in Edo State. The findings of the study, however, disagreed with Ezenwaji (2018) position that quality assurance officers lack facilities and equipment for school inspection which prevents them from carrying out an effective inspection to enhance high job performance among teachers in Primary Schools in the South East Zone of Nigeria. Subject-based inspection is a specialized inspection conducted by quality assurance officers in subject areas in which they are

specialists. It requires the quality assurance officers to visit and obtain information about teaching and learning situations from teachers in their subject areas and other aspects of school endeavour to enable them to make provision for improving the weak areas through planning and formulation of policies that would maintain the standard of teaching in various subjects that are contained in the curriculum. Textbooks, instructional materials, qualifications of teachers, and teaching methods are the major focus of subject-based inspection. It is usually conducted based on the request of a school to have a centre for external examinations like the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). Equally, when a school intends to add new subjects to the existing ones, before introducing such subjects, the chief inspector needs to send the quality assurance officers with the knowledge of the proposed subjects to assess the readiness of the school in the areas of instructional resources. A school could be permitted to introduce new subjects if the chief inspector is satisfied with the reports by quality assurance officers who have visited such schools.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings:

The study concluded that there is a poor impact of full-general inspection on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja.

The study further concluded that subject-based inspection does not create a high impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The study recommended that the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Secondary Education Board should mandate all principals to implement all the observations of the quality assurance officers during full-general inspection exercise to enable teachers to overcome their teaching weaknesses and become effective in performing their teaching responsibilities.
2. The laid down policy on subject-based inspection as stated in the National Policy on Education in terms of using subject experts during inspection need to be strictly adhered to by the FCT Education sector so that teachers could be inspected by specialists in their various subjects. Such an approach would help quality assurance officers to properly guide and direct teachers to improve their teaching skills.

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